

STRUCTURAL BEHAVIOUR OF REINFORCED CONCRETE COLUMNS REINFORCED WITH VARIOUS MATERIALS

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1 Abstract

This paper presents a proposed method of producing new circular reinforced concrete columns reinforced with various types of reinforcing materials. The experimental program includes casting and testing up to failure sixteen circular columns having the same dimensions of 72 mm in diameter and 1m long were tested under concentric compression loadings. The experimental program comprises five designations series. The main variables are the type of reinforcing materials metallic or non metallic, the number of layers; volume fraction of reinforcement, specific surface area of reinforcing materials, incorporating of bamboo in the core of the test specimens. The main objectives are to evaluate the effectiveness of employing three types of FRP with different technical methods of strengthening concrete columns. To make comparative study between strengthening concrete columns and concrete columns reinforced with welded steel meshes, fiber glass meshes, polypropylene meshes, and bamboo with meshes. The results of an experimental investigation to examine the effectiveness of these produced columns are reported and discussed including strength, deformation, cracking, ductility and energy absorption properties of the test specimens. Specimens strengthened with FRP, Aramid emphasized more effective and efficient more than hydride materials. High ductility and energy absorption properties could be obtained of ferrocement columns. New reinforced concrete

Columns were developed with high strength, crack resistance, high ductility and energy absorption properties. High ductility and energy absorption properties could be obtained of ferrocement columns.

Introduction

In the last few decades, incidence of failures of reinforced concrete structures has been seen widely because of increasing service loads and/or durability problems. The economic losses due to such failures are billions of dollars. Mansur and Paramasivan [1] carried out an experimental investigation in 1990 on ferrocement box-section short columns with and without concrete infills under axial and eccentric compression. The major parameters of the study were the types, arrangements, and volume fraction of reinforcement. Test results indicated that a ferrocement box-section can be used as a structural column. Welded wire mesh has been found to perform better than an equivalent amount of woven mesh. In 1994, Kaushik et al. [2] carried out an investigation for ferrocement encased concrete columns. They have investigated short circular as well as square columns with unreinforced and reinforced cores. It was seen that the ferrocement encasement increases the strength and ductility of the columns for both axial and eccentric loading conditions. Another interesting research work was done by Ahmed et al. [3] to investigate the possibility of using ferrocement as a retrofit material for masonry columns. Uniaxial compression tests were performed on three uncoated brick columns, six coated brick columns with 25 mm plaster and another six columns coated with 25 mm thick layer of ferrocement. The study demonstrated that the use ferrocement coating strengthens brick columns significantly and improves their cracking resistance.

Nedwell et al. [4] conducted a preliminary investigation into the repair of short square columns using ferrocement. A short program was undertaken to provide some information regarding the effect of ferrocement repair on short columns subjected to axial loadings. It was found that the use of ferrocement retrofit coating increases the apparent stiffness of the columns and significantly improves the ultimate load carrying capacity.

Experimental Program

Sixteen circular composite columns having the dimensions of 72 mm in diameter and 1000 mm length were cast and tested until failure. The concrete mix for the test specimens was designed to obtain compressive strength at 28-days age of 32 MPa. The mix proportions were 2 sand: 1 cement, water cement ratio was 0.35 and 1.5% super plasticizer by weight of cement. The concrete slump was found to be 120 mm and a density of 2300 Kg/m³. Various types of reinforcing and strengthening materials were employed as shown in Fig. 1. All specimens were tested under central uni axial compression loadings by using Dartec Testing Machine of capacity 250 KN as shown in Fig.2

Test Results and Discussion

Figs. 3 and 4 show load –displacement curves for columns C1-C8 and C9-C16 respectively. The first crack, serviceability and ultimate loads and their corresponding deformations are listed in Table 1, while Figs. 5-7 Show first crack of tested columns, serviceability and ultimate loads of tested columns. Figs.8 and 9 Show ductility ratio and energy absorption of tested columns. It is interesting to note from Table1 that for columns C2, C3 and C7, which reinforced with 3w.m, 2 w.m. and One layer w.m that the corresponding ultimate loads were 218, 194 and 115 KN respectively While column C13, which reinforced with one layer w.m+ bamboo of Φ 30 mm inserted in its core reached 148 KN, which is about 29% higher than that of column C7. Comparing the ultimate loads obtained for columns C6 and C8, which were reinforced with one and two layers of tensor mesh SS40 were 95 and 173 KN respectively. Comparing the ultimate loads obtained for columns C9, C10 and C11, which were strengthened with carbon fibers with black lines, partially located yellow carbon fibers and wholly

yellow carbon fibers were 181, 177 and 154.2 KN respectively. It is observed that partially adhesive carbon fibers are significant. Comparing the ultimate loads reached for columns C14, C15 and C16, which were strengthened with wholly yellow carbon fibers, carbon fibers with black lines, and partially located two layers of carbon fibers with black lines were 148, 138.3 and 185 KN respectively. It is worth to strength columns by means of carbon fibers irrespective of their types. The average strength gain is about 157 KN, which is about 2.15 times that of control test specimen, column C5. Fig.10 shows the cracking patterns of tested columns. There is no spalling of concrete cover for most of specimens that is predominant.

Table 1 Test Results of Column Specimens

Col. No.	F.C KN	Pse KN	Pultim. KN	dis,fc... (mm)	dis,ma (mm)	Ductility Ratio	Energy Abs.KNmm
C1	75.	78	124.3	4.178	6.001	1.44	330.4
C2	129	135	217.9	0.52	0.914	1.76	97.4
C3	116	121	194.0	1.903	2.317	1.22	97.5
C4	42	66	105.0	0.563	0.935	1.66	36.98
C5	25	66	72.98	0.279	1.022	3.66	41.74
C6	38	45	95.92	1.195	1.245	1.04	16.09
C7	57	60	115.0	3.381	4.294	1.27	189.18
C8	103	108	173.1	2.254	5.363	2.38	512.06
C9	105	110	180.4	4.83	6.227	1.29	340.2
C10	106	110	176.7	4.858	5.119	1.05	149.43
C11	92	98	157.1	4.502	5.096	1.13	177.70
C12	39	69	111.0	0.924	1.787	1.93	106.57
C13	81	92	147.9	1.174	1.21	1.03	31.71
C14	88	92	147.9	0.8	1.693	2.12	139.11
C15	83	86	138.3	1.865	2.006	1.08	112.16
C16	111	116	185.3	2.406	2.586	1.075	124.99

Fig. 2 Test-set-up.

Conclusions

Based on the results and observations of the experimental investigation presented in this paper. The following conclusions can be drawn as follows:

1. High strength and durable columns were developed with high ductility and energy absorption properties which are very useful for dynamic applications.
2. There is a great saving in reinforcing materials. Reinforcing concrete columns with tensar SS40 is effective with high strength gain arrived to 2.4 times that of conventionally reinforced concrete columns.
3. Irrespective of the shape and type of carbon fibers employed in strengthening concrete columns, there is significant increase in strength reached about 215% strength gain comparable with that of reinforced concrete columns.

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Fig. 1 Reinforcing Materials and Reinforcement Configurations of Columns

Figure (3) Load-Displacement Curves for Columns C1-C8

Figure (4) Load-Displacement Curves for Columns C9 – C16

Fig. 10 Cracking Patterns of Tested Columns.